

Why Two Rocks Have Twoness

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Abstract

Two rocks sit in a forest with no one to see them. Did they have twoness? The question is an entry point into the nature of mathematical objects and where they come from. Three standard answers—Platonism, formalism, and naïve realism—each fail by isolating one element of a relationship and discarding the others. This paper argues that mathematical abstractions like twoness are constructed by material minds from material regularities, not discovered in a mind-independent realm. The cognitive tools that produce abstraction evolved because stable environments rewarded regularity detection. The historical and archaeological record confirms that abstraction emerged from material practice—weaving, counting, measurement—not prior to it. Once sufficiently detached from practice, abstraction becomes an immaterial rule system, real and constraining, whose internal geometry exceeds what its constructors could survey in advance. This is why mathematics feels like discovery. Notational innovations then expand what minds can perceive in systems that already exist, driving mathematics beyond its material origins without severing the connection to them. Mathematical constraint operates at two levels: matter doing what matter does, and rules generating their own internal geometry. The fit between them is not mysterious. The abstraction was built from the world it describes. The story we tell about it is reversed.

Keywords: Mathematical ontology; Abstraction; Material constraint; Idealisation; Mind-dependence; Rule systems; Regularity

1 Introduction

[T]he laws of nature are written in the language of mathematics
...(Wigner 1960, p. 6)

Two rocks are sitting in a forest with no one to see them. How many rocks are there? Before anyone arrived to observe them they had mass, position, and various other mind-independent properties. But did they have twoness?

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The question sounds almost childish. Of course there were two rocks. Count them: one, two—not none, not three—two! But the counting is precisely what is at issue. Counting is something a mind does. The question is whether twoness was there before the counting, waiting to be found, or whether it arrived with the counter.

This is not a question about the rocks. It is a question about the nature of mathematical objects and where they come from. If the universe and all its interactions are purely material—belonging to physical configurations in specific places and times—then what is the role of mathematical laws in physics? Mathematics is not material, but it is nonetheless constrained. It forces representations into correspondence regardless of substrate. A world cannot be both one where only material interactions are real and one where immaterial constraints genuinely govern.

Whether two rocks have twoness is an entry point for thinking about this. And it turns out to be surprisingly difficult to answer without either smuggling in a hidden assumption or committing to a position with consequences one might not have intended.

There are three standard answers.

The Platonist says twoness exists independently of minds, matter, and time. Two is an ideal. The rocks instantiate that pre-existing abstract object—the number two—that would exist even if the rocks did not, even if no mind had ever counted anything. Mathematical objects are discovered, not invented. Like explorers, mathematicians find what was always there.

The formalist says twoness is constituted by a formal symbolic system. There is no number two floating in an abstract realm. There are only the rules of arithmetic, and within those rules, two is whatever the rules say it is. Mathematical existence is existence within a system. Outside the system, the question has no content.

The naïve realist says twoness is simply a property of the rocks, directly perceived. There are two of them. What more needs to be said?

Each answer fails in a specific way.

Platonism preserves the necessity and universality of mathematics but at a steep ontological price. It requires a realm of abstract objects that exist independently of matter and mind, that cannot be perceived by any physical sense, and whose relationship to the material world—why mathematics describes physical reality so precisely—remains deeply mysterious. The Platonist buys mathematical certainty by writing a cheque on metaphysics that is very difficult to cash. There is also an empirical problem. If mathematical objects are discovered rather than constructed, one would predict a cultural convergence. Instead the record shows that structural differences track material choices: base-5 from counting on one hand, base-10 from both hands, base-20 from fingers and toes (Overmann 2025a). The substrate shapes the output which is not what discovery looks like.

Formalism avoids the metaphysical extravagance but loses the sense in which mathematical constraints are genuinely forcing. If twoness is just whatever the rules of arithmetic say, why can the rules not say something different? And

why does arithmetic, developed as an abstract exercise, turn out to describe the material world with such precision? Formalism makes mathematics safe but strips it of explanatory power.

Naïve realism seems closest to common sense but dissolves on examination. Twoness is not a physical property like mass. You cannot measure it with an instrument. Two rocks and two stars all have twoness, but they share no physical property. Whatever twoness is, it is not straightforwardly in the rocks.

There is a further wrinkle worth noting at the outset. Twoness does not attach to arbitrary collections of things. We do not naturally look at a grain of sand and an elephant and say, there are two objects. Quantity rides on category. Before a mind can count, it must first perceive the things being counted as belonging together in some relevant respect—two rocks, two sisters, two animals, two obstacles. The category precedes the number. This is not a trivial observation. It means that the abstraction of quantity is never a bare cognitive act performed on raw matter. It is always performed on matter already perceived through a categorical lens. And those categories are themselves abstractions—built from material regularities, from the real similarities and differences that a stable material world presents to minds that evolved to detect them. Twoness, it turns out, requires not one abstraction but two. The rocks have to be rocks before they can be two.

The problem runs deeper than the ontological price. Platonism faces an enumeration dilemma. Either the number two exists as an ideal waiting to be attached to things—in which case a mind is needed to do the attaching, which undermines mind-independence—or twoness pre-exists as a property of every possible combination of two objects across every possible category in every possible world. The second option does not simplify the ontology. It is a combinatoric explosion that needs to account for all the $1 \dots N$ possible aggregation of objects in the universe. The paper argues that both horns of this dilemma dissolve once mathematical abstractions like twoness are understood as mind-dependent constructions from material regularities, rather than mind-independent discoveries.

2 Evolving Concepts

The eye is not a general-purpose truth detector. It is a highly evolved, contextually adapted response to the specific feature of a particular material environment. The eye sees the way it does because of the material arrangements of the environment in which it evolved. The brain perceives the environment the way it does because its cognitive architecture has co-evolved with the eye to make survival choices—information it carries about the spatial configuration of matter.

In well-lit environments, creatures with more accurate visual systems detected predators sooner, located food more reliably, and navigated obstacles more successfully than creatures with poorer vision. The eye is what selection pressure produces when light is available and the ability to process it confers

survival advantage.

The corollary is exact. In permanent darkness, no eyes. Cave-dwelling fish that migrate into lightless environments lose their eyes. The organs are metabolically costly, and where they purchase nothing they are selected against. The eye does not persist in darkness out of fidelity to some general principle of visual truth. It exists only where it pays, and it is tuned to the environment that produced it, not to reality in any universal sense.

The human eye is blind to most of the electromagnetic spectrum. It is fooled by a wide range of optical illusions. It has a structural blind spot. It is a good-enough instrument for navigating a particular kind of material world under particular lighting conditions—nothing more, and nothing less.

There is one additional point. Evolution relies on regularities in the environment. Fitness—selection and adaptation towards an environment—requires regularity. The dinosaurs did not survive a moment of environmental rupture precisely because it failed the regularity requirements of their adaptations. Mammals emerged and found their niche. Humans evolved because of a material regularity in their environment. And as a part of their evolution, they developed cognitive capacities to manage environmental change by re-engineering that environment—building shelter, growing crops, and so forth.

The same logic applies to the cognitive tools that produce abstraction. Minds evolved in stable material regions because creatures capable of detecting regularities, generalising across instances, and building portable representations of their environment navigated that environment more successfully than creatures that could not. The capacity to notice that two of something share a structural property—that the twoness is the same in both cases—was adaptive because the material world was stable enough that such regularities persisted and could be exploited. A mind that could abstract quantity from particular instances could count, plan, predict, and coordinate in ways that conferred real survival advantage. The abstraction was selected for because the environment rewarded it.

The honey bee *Apis mellifera* has a brain smaller than a sesame seed. Their evolution as foragers has endowed them with a series of cognitive skill including numerosity (judgements up to a quantity of four) (Howard et al. 2018), rudimentary arithmetic (addition and subtraction of one) and the representation of zero (Howard et al. 2019). They can abstract, detecting structural regularities across materially different instances, generalised and applied to novel situations. They would appear to have *twoness* (or some version of it) in their mathematical repertoire.

This is a different instantiation of the same underlying sensitivity to material regularities not a failure of bee-twoness. The bee has proto-twoness. The human mathematician has twoness elaborated into number theory. These are recognisably members of the same family even if they are not the same thing. They are different levels of abstraction (but nonetheless abstractions) from the same kind of material constraint, produced by different minds shaped by different evolutionary pressures in the same stable material region.

This matters for the argument in two directions. First, it confirms that

abstraction is not a sudden cognitive miracle unique to human minds. It is what can evolve when a stable material world selects for regularity detection. Second, and more consequentially, it suggests that twoness is not a single fixed concept with one correct instantiation. It is a family of increasingly detached abstractions from material quantity, and the human symbolic version—however powerful—is one member of that family, not the definitive one.

This is not a claim that mathematics is merely a survival tool. It is a claim about origins. The cognitive machinery that eventually produces number theory, geometry, and formal logic was shaped by selection pressure in a material environment stable enough to make regularity detection pay. Had the local material region been genuinely chaotic—had configurations dissolved before they could be recognised as sharing structural properties, had no regularities persisted long enough to be exploited—no such mental or synaptic machinery would have evolved. There would have been nothing to abstract from, and no advantage in the capacity to abstract.

The point can be stated as a counterfactual. In a region of the universe where material relationships did not stabilise, where there were no repeating structures, no consistent ratios, no reliable spatial or temporal regularities, minds of the kind that do mathematics would not arise. Not because mathematics would be false in such a region, but because the preconditions for the cognitive tools that produce mathematics would be absent. No stable matter, no selection pressure for regularity detection. No regularity detection, no abstraction. No abstraction, no mathematics.

This dissolves what Eugene Wigner called the unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics in the natural sciences (Wigner 1960). Wigner observed that mathematical structures developed with no practical application in mind—complex numbers, non-Euclidean geometries, group theory—repeatedly turn out to be exactly the language required to describe physical reality. He found this deeply mysterious, a gift that neither physicists nor mathematicians could explain. The mystery, however, arises from a hidden assumption: that mathematics developed independently of the material world and therefore its fit with that world requires explanation. Once the assumption is removed, the mystery dissolves. Mathematics was developed by minds shaped by that world, using cognitive tools selected for their capacity to detect and exploit the regularities of that world. It did not arise independently of the minds doing work in a material world. The fit is expected, not miraculous. We are here, doing mathematics, because we are in a region where the cognitive tools that produce mathematics were adaptive. The question could not be asked from a region where it has no answer.

A further implication follows. The mathematics we have is tuned to the regularities that our cognitive architecture was shaped to detect. It is not tuned to all possible regularities that a stable material region might contain. Just as the human eye is sensitive to a narrow band of the electromagnetic spectrum and blind to the rest, human mathematical cognition may be sensitive to a particular range of structural regularities and systematically blind to others—not because those regularities do not exist, but because no selection pressure ever produced

the tools for perceiving them. This possibility is not a sceptical conclusion about the validity of existing mathematics. It is an observation about the scope of any cognitive tool shaped by local adaptive pressure. The eye evolved to see what mattered in a particular environment. It sees that well. What lies outside its range was simply never the matter at hand.

3 Material before Law

The Western philosophical tradition has a recurring temptation to treat reason, logic, and order as prior to matter. This idea appears at the very beginning of the Gospel of St John (1:1): *In the beginning was the Word (λόγος)*—the rational principle, the structuring intelligence that precedes and organises matter.

The temptation is understandable. By the time philosophers arrive to ask questions about origins, reason is already fully present and matter appears as the thing reason contemplates. The sequence leading to the point of contemplation is invisible. What remains visible is the contemplation itself. It is easy to mistake the last thing in the sequence for the first.

The historical and archaeological record of how mathematical knowledge actually developed confirms this sequence—and it does so without philosophical argument.

The earliest mathematical artefacts are not proofs or formal systems. They are tallies, counts, and measures embedded in material practice—fingers, clay tablets recording grain allocations, knotted cords tracking quantities, notched bones whose purpose was almost certainly enumeration (d’Errico et al. 2018; Overmann 2025b). The abstraction emerged from practice, slowly, over millennia, as regularities encountered through doing were gradually detached from their particular material contexts and recognised as structural properties that persisted across different instances.

Weaving provides one of the most instructive examples. The constraints of the loom are material and immediate (see Postrel (2020, Ch. 3)). On the warp-weighted looms of ancient Greece, the number of weft threads used to construct the border determined what patterns were possible in the main cloth. If that count was prime, no repeated pattern could fit evenly across the width—the threads would not divide. If the count had factors, patterns could repeat at any common interval. The weaver did not need to know what a prime number was, only that certain thread counts were obstinate and others accommodating—knowledge acquired through the resistance of the material itself, through bundles of thread that came out even or did not, through patterns that worked and patterns that failed. What Euclid would later formalise in *Elements*—the propositions about odd and even numbers, common factors, and relative primeness that historians have struggled to explain as pure abstraction—were already embedded in weaving practice before Euclid wrote anything (Harlizius-Klück 2016).

The method of bundling threads to find remainders is a direct material analogue of reciprocal subtraction, the algorithm for finding common factors

that appears in Book VII of the *Elements*. Nor is this connection between weaving and mathematics confined to ancient Greece or to any single tradition. West Africa had a rich tradition of strip weaving (Gilfoy 1987). The patterns are complex and require systematic exploitation of repeat intervals, common factors, and symmetry operations—reflection, rotation, translation—applied thread by thread across a narrow strip and then multiplied when the strips are assembled into a full cloth. The mathematics is material. When the strips are combined to form whole cloth, each strip must carry a precise repeating pattern—a problem in modular arithmetic conducted entirely through material practice, without reference to any formal mathematical system.

The Andean tradition makes the same point from a different angle (Brezine 2009). Weavers working with equipment no more elaborate than two sticks and a belt produced cloth of extraordinary structural complexity—cloth whose mathematical structure, when later analysed, turned out to involve binary matrices, symmetry groups, and combinatorial pattern generation. The complexity was achieved not through mechanical automation but through algorithms held in the weaver’s head and fingers, with improvisation possible at every pick. The same constraint space was being navigated through a completely different cognitive and material architecture from the European floor loom, arriving at correspondent and verifiable results. Neither architecture owned the mathematics. Both were constrained by what stable, structured cloth requires.

In each case mathematical abstraction was preceded by practice. It emerged from it, as structural regularities encountered through material work that were gradually detached from their context and recognised as properties of number and space itself. Euclid did not invent geometry. He organised, formalised, and extended abstractions that had been developing from material practice over centuries (Imhausen 2016).

Counting emerged from the material requirements of managing resources—tracking animals, allocating food, recording obligations. The abstraction of number from particular countable things was a gradual process of recognising that the structural property shared by two rocks, two hunters, and two seasons was the same property, detachable from any particular material instance and manipulable on its own terms. “Societies that don’t use material devices to represent and manipulate numbers, as it turns out, have very few concepts of numbers” (Overmann 2025a, p. 6). The portability of the abstraction—the fact that you could reason about two without specifying two of what—was itself an achievement that took time and practice to consolidate.

The point is historical and ontological. Abstraction does not float free of matter and then descend to organise it. It arises from material practice and then, once sufficiently detached, can be explored on its own terms as an immaterial rule system. The direction of travel is from the material to the abstract, not from the abstract to the material. The logos that eventually emerges—the formal, portable, self-contained rule system—is the product of the sequence, not its origin.

This has a direct consequence for the question of whether mathematical structure pre-existed the minds that discovered it. Twoness evolved in bees as

in humans, through the consequential interaction with a material world. Neither bees nor humans *discovered* twoness.

While bees may not understand twoness as we do, material configurations instantiated structural regularities that minds, through practice, eventually abstracted (and in the case of humans, named). The regularities were there—in farming flood plains, in the loom, in two rocks—in the sense that the material world was doing what it does, consistently and indifferently. But the structure as structure—abstracted, named, incorporated into a portable rule system—was not there until minds arrived to build it from what the material world presented. Daston’s history of rules traces precisely this sequence: practical knowledge begins embedded in material contexts, in the hands of craftsmen, surveyors, and merchants, and is only gradually detached from those contexts, formalised, and elevated into general principles that appear to have always existed (Daston 2022). The appearance of prior existence is a product of the formalisation, not evidence of it. What looks like discovery is the last stage of a long process of construction that began in matter and ended in logos.

This is what all successful abstraction looks like. The power is in the fit between the handle and the material configuration, not in the prior existence of the essence the handle purports to name. Logos is a very good handle but it is not the origin. It is what hands, working in matter, eventually built—or was seen to have built by others watching the process.¹

The erasure of this sequence was evitable. Asper’s account of the two cultures of Greek mathematics documents how theoretical mathematics distinguished itself from practical mathematics through a deliberate game of social distinction—what he calls, following Bourdieu, a *game of distinction*—in which the upper-class theorist distanced himself from the hired professional and craftsman whose material practice had generated the abstractions theoretical mathematics then formalised (Asper 2009). The genre conventions of theoretical mathematics—its impersonal rhetoric, its studied silence about applications and origins—enforced that distance systematically. As Asper observes, theoretical mathematics was always an epiphenomenon of or marginal distinction from strong practical traditions, however invisible those traditions were made to appear (p.128).

The weaving evidence already examined in this paper illustrates precisely the kind of practical knowledge Asper’s account describes as suppressed. The constraints of the loom—the primeness of thread counts, factors, the modular arithmetic of repeating patterns—were being navigated by weavers across Greece before Euclid wrote anything. The mathematics was real, it was being done, and it was being done by people who were socially invisible. The propositions in Book VII of the *Elements* about common factors and relative

¹The physicist Hendrik B. G. Casimir recounted a story about the theoretical physicist Paul Dirac that perfectly illustrates this. “It is told that he [Dirac] once watched a woman for quite some time while she was knitting. Finally, after having understood to his satisfaction the topology of the stitches, he said, ‘You could also do it a different way,’ and embarked on a description. The lady cut him short. ‘Of course you can,’ she said. ‘That is purl [stitch]’” (Casimir 2010, p. 74).

primeness did not descend from a theoretical realm; their material roots went unacknowledged.

Platonism provided the philosophical ratification for this erasure. If mathematical forms exist independently of matter and mind, eternally and perfectly, then the material practice that produced access to them is mere approximation. It is a groping towards truth that the theorist, freed from material constraint, can grasp directly. The social hierarchy is written into the ontology. The artisan works with imperfect instantiations of ideal forms. The philosopher contemplates the forms themselves. On this account, the weavers were never doing mathematics. They were producing cloth. That Euclid's number theory is the formalisation of what practice already knew becomes not just invisible but inconceivable. The appearance that mathematics was always abstract and theoretical is partly an artefact of who got to write the history and what philosophical framework made their erasure look like metaphysical necessity rather than social choice.

4 Immaterial Rule Systems

Once abstraction has detached a structural regularity from its material origin, something new becomes possible. The abstraction can be elaborated into a rule system—a set of stipulated relationships that can be explored on its own terms, without reference to the material practice that generated it. The result is a distinctive kind of object: neither a physical thing, nor a Platonic entity floating in an abstract realm, nor a merely subjective mental state. It is an immaterial rule system, and it requires its own ontological category.

A modern example serves better here than an ancient one, and the reason for choosing it is itself part of the argument. In 1970, the mathematician John Horton Conway stipulated four simple rules governing whether cells on an infinite grid would be alive or dead in the next generation, depending on how many live neighbours they currently had (Gardner 1970). The rules took minutes to state. What followed from them was inexhaustible. Gliders—stable configurations that move across the grid. Oscillators that pulse with fixed periodicity. Self-replicating structures. And, most remarkably, universal computation—the Game of Life can simulate any Turing machine (Rendell 2016). This last point is worthy of underscoring. A universal Turing machine can compute anything that is computable. Every algorithm, every formal proof, every mathematical derivation that can in principle be executed, can in principle be encoded and run within Conway's four rules. The entire edifice of symbolic mathematics, if you know how to programme it, runs on that stipulation.

None of this was designed into the rules. It fell out of the internal geometry of the system when the rules were explored. Conway stipulated four rules and was then, along with everyone else, surprised by what the stipulation achieved. He did not discover these structures in a Platonic realm. The Game of Life is not just a vivid illustration of emergence. It is, in a precise technical sense, the most minimal maximally powerful example available—a construction so simple

it can be stated in a sentence, yet so rich that extracting its full consequences would require deep insight into what the rules allow, insight that remains genuinely non-trivial and in important respects inexhaustible. The glider was not waiting somewhere to be found. It was a structural consequence of the stipulation, invisible until the system was explored by minds willing to look carefully at what four rules actually implied. This is what an immaterial rule system looks like from the inside: a construction whose internal geometry exceeds what the constructor could survey in advance, generating the phenomenology of discovery from the fact of exploration. The surprise is real. The Platonic realm is unnecessary. The enumeration dilemma that Platonism cannot escape dissolves here. Twoness was never free-floating across all possible pairings of objects in the universe, because twoness always rides on category, and categories are themselves constructions that arrived with the minds that built them.

The possibility of universal computation was not sitting somewhere waiting for Conway to arrive. It is internal to the stipulation. Before the four rules were written down, there was no system within which that possibility could be said to obtain. And crucially, recognising that the possibility was there—actually programming a Turing machine within the Game of Life—required minds capable of perceiving what the rules afforded. The affordance was real once the rules existed. It was not available before. This is the structure of all mathematical construction: stipulate the rules, and the internal geometry becomes available for exploration. Do not stipulate them, and there is nothing to explore.

The rules of the Game of Life are immaterial. No particular grid is required for them to hold. The system can be run on paper, on a computer, or in the head of someone who has memorised the rules. The material instantiation is a vehicle, not constitutive of the system. Remove every computer that has ever run it and the rules remain, intact, in the minds that know them. Remove the minds and the rules cease to exist. There is no Life-realm where the glider persists independently of every mind that has ever stipulated or learned the four rules that generate it.

The Game of Life arrives at an immaterial rule system almost *de novo*—four rules stipulated by a mathematician at a desk, with no pretence of describing the material world. Mathematics more typically takes a different route to the same destination. Mathematical rule systems are usually abstracted from material regularities and then elaborated far beyond their origins through idealisation. The circle is the clearest case. Circular(-ish) material configurations existed before minds: orbits, eddies, the cross-section of a tree trunk. None of them is perfectly circular. The material world does not traffic in idealisations. The circle as a geometric object—perfectly round, with a determinate ratio of circumference to diameter—was constructed by minds willing to strip away material *imperfection* and ask what a *perfect* version would be. π fell out of that construction. It did not pre-exist it. There was no ratio waiting in the orbits to be discovered. There were approximately circular orbits, and there were minds that idealised them into a rule system, and within that rule system π is what it is necessarily—not because nature decreed it, but because the construction

did. Two routes, then, into the same kind of object: stipulation nearly from scratch, and idealisation from material practice. In both cases what results is an immaterial rule system whose internal geometry is real, constraining, and richer than its origins suggested.

Once a mathematical rule system is stipulated, its internal geometry is fixed. What follows from the rules is non negotiable, and it is typically richer than the minds that stipulated the rules could have anticipated. This is why mathematics feels like discovery. Euler did not know his identity before he derived it ($e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0$). The surprise is real. But it is the surprise of exploring a constructed system whose internal consequences exceed what any finite mind could survey in advance—not the surprise of finding something that was always there. The explorer and the architect are the same person, separated by time.

Gödel's incompleteness theorems fit naturally into this account, and do not threaten it. Sufficiently powerful formal systems contain truths that cannot be reached from within the system using its own rules. This is precisely what one would expect from a finitely constructed rule system being explored by finite minds with bounded access profiles. The incompleteness is a structural feature of the system that follows from its own construction. It is not a crack in the universe or a hint of a Platonic realm beyond the rules. It is the internal geometry of the system being richer than any single architecture can exhaust—a consequence of construction, not evidence of transcendence. Different formal systems, or different cognitive architectures navigating the same system, may reach regions that symbolic manipulation alone cannot. The incompleteness is expected. It confirms rather than embarrasses the account.

The immaterial rule system is therefore what abstraction becomes when it fully detaches from material practice. It originated in matter—in the rope, the loom, the two rocks—passed through the hands of practitioners who encountered its constraints bodily, and was gradually formalised into a portable, self-contained structure that can be explored without reference to its origins. The logos that the Gospel of St John places at the beginning is, in fact, what the sequence eventually produces. It is the far end of the process, not the start of it. And it remains immaterial not because it transcends matter but because matter was never what constituted it. What constitutes it are the rules, and rules are sustained by minds, which are themselves material.

Tic-tac-toe is not tokens on a board, it is a set of rules in players' minds. Remove every such mind and the game vanishes even if the tokens remain. Mathematical rule systems are immaterial in exactly the same sense. They are real and constraining while minds hold them, and they vanish when no mind does.

The rules of abstract systems are ours. The constraints that follow from them are not.

5 Tools, Notation, and the Expansion of Mathematical Perception

The sequence from matter to abstraction does not have a natural terminus. Abstraction produces tools, tools afford new perception, new perception extends the abstraction, and extended abstraction demands better tools. The mutual constitution of tool and concept is as central to the history of mathematics as the original abstraction from material practice.

There is, however, a more fundamental point about tools that precedes any particular example. The most basic mathematical tool is externalisation itself. Mathematical reasoning is constrained by the limits of working memory. The unaided human mind can hold only a small number of items in working memory simultaneously (Miller 1956). A mathematical proof of any complexity exceeds that capacity in memory by orders of magnitude. The solution is material. Externalise the intermediate steps onto a surface—clay tablet, papyrus, blackboard, page—so that each step, once written, frees cognitive resources to perceive the next. The material surface is not a record of thinking that happened elsewhere. It is part of the thinking (Overmann 2025a).

The material externalisation is why mathematical proof developed as serialised symbolic sequence. It is the architecture that fits the cognitive tools available to minds shaped by evolution with working memory limits. The notation is the workaround. The serialisation is a contingent feature of one cognitive architecture, not a constitutive feature of mathematical procedure (Reidpath 2026).

The decimal system and the placeholder zero illustrate the notational point with minimal complexity. Zero as a concept—the number that represents absence—is philosophically important. But zero as a positional placeholder is a notational innovation, and its consequences were not philosophical but operational (Seife 2000; Kaplan 2000). Arithmetic with large numbers became tractable. Calculations that had required specialists became routine, and tractability is not a neutral property. When a class of operations becomes easy to perform, it becomes possible to notice structural regularities across those operations that were invisible when each calculation was a laborious individual achievement. The notation did not just record mathematical knowledge. It expanded the range of structure that was perceivable as mathematical.

Leibniz's notation for calculus makes the same point more sharply (Cajori 1929). Newton and Leibniz developed calculus independently and substantially simultaneously. The underlying mathematics was, in the relevant sense, the same. But Leibniz's notation— $\frac{dy}{dx}$ for the derivative, \int for the integral—was generative in a way that Newton's fluxion notation was not. Leibniz made the operations perceivable as manipulable objects. You could operate on $\frac{dy}{dx}$ as if it were a fraction, extend the notation to partial derivatives, apply it to new classes of problems. The notation afforded mathematical moves that Newton's notation did not make visible.

Not all notational innovations begin at a desk. Some are lifted directly out

of material practice.

The Jacquard loom, developed in the early nineteenth century, made the binary structure already present in the manual loom explicit and mechanical—wef threads sliding above or below the warp—on or off (Essinger 2007). Jacquard did not invent binary encoding. He lifted it out of the weaver’s hands and into a notational system—the punched card—that could be read by a machine. The notation made the structure of weaving perceivable as discrete instruction. And discrete instruction, once perceivable as a general form, could migrate to new material domains. Herman Hollerith generalised the punched card as a medium for encoding discrete binary information to support the analysis of data from the United States census of 1890 (Austrian 1982). The notational tool developed from weaving practice had been lifted entirely free of looms and thread and applied to the thoroughly different material problem of counting people. The structure travelled because it was abstract enough to travel—not because anyone designed it to.

This is what the mutual constitution of tool and abstraction looks like across historical time. Mathematics does not advance only when minds perceive new regularities in matter. It advances when new notational tools make new structure perceivable in rule systems that already exist.

Daston’s history of rules traces a related movement: practical knowledge that begins embedded in material contexts is gradually formalised into general principles that appear to have always existed (Daston 2022). The present argument extends that observation. Formalisation is not the end of the sequence. Each formalisation produces tools—notational, conceptual, material—that make new structure perceivable in the formalised system, generating further abstraction, further formalisation, further tools. The logos that appears to precede matter is always, on closer inspection, the current far end of a sequence that began in matter and has not yet reached its terminus.

6 Conclusion

Two rocks are sitting in a forest with no one to see them.

The three standard answers to the twoness question each fail in the same direction. Platonism places twoness outside mind and matter entirely, in a realm that requires no explanation of how minds ever access it. Naïve realism places it entirely in the rocks, where no instrument can find it. Formalism places it entirely in the rules, with no account of why those rules fit the world they were abstracted from. Each position isolates one element of a relationship and discards the others.

The material emergence account holds all three in relation. The rocks had real structural properties. They were stable, consistent, and mind-independent. The minds that eventually counted them were material products of the same stable world, shaped by evolution to detect precisely the regularities that world presented. Twoness is what emerged from that interaction. Twoness is not discovered in a Platonic realm, nor read directly off the rocks, nor arbitrar-

ily stipulated. It is constructed by material minds from material regularities and then elaborated, through idealisation and stipulation, into immaterial rule systems whose internal geometry is real and constraining.

Mathematical constraint operates at two distinct levels. At the level of the material world, two threads do not divide into three without remainder—that is not mathematics, it is matter doing what matter does, indifferently and necessarily. At the level of the rule system, once the rules are stipulated their internal consequences are fixed. Change the rules and you get different results, but given the rules, the geometry is determined. Mathematics abstracts the first kind of constraint into a system that generates the second. The fit between them is not mysterious. The abstraction was built from the material regularities it describes.

The mathematical physicist, Roger Penrose observed that all physics is mathematics but not all mathematics is physics (Penrose 2007). He drew Platonist conclusions from the asymmetry. The present account explains it differently. Once abstraction detaches from material practice and rule systems begin exploring their own internal geometry, the exploration outstrips its origins. The unrealised mathematics is not evidence of a separate realm. It is evidence of how generative stipulation is.

The circle did not know its own ratio. We built the ratio from circles. The construction was material in origin, immaterial in form, and constraining in consequence. It is what minds do with matter when the world is stable enough to reward the effort and does not require mind independent ideals.

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